

19 Partners

10 Countries

Industrial Manufacturing Strategies

42 Months

6m Euros
in funding

For distributed control and resilient, rapidly responsive and reconfigurable supply chains.

Funded by
the European Union

The Project

Time Series,
NoSQL, SQL

Simulation

Optimisation

Predictive
Analytics

Industrial Metaverse
Simulations | Digital Twins

Transition of modular technology to sustainable production.		
Significant advancement of modular technologies.		
Improved information flow and awareness of modular technologies.		

MODUL4R aims to advance manufacturing with robust and autonomous modular production lines and supply chains. These advancements will allow low-volume production of new products, as well as capacities to rapidly adapt to unexpected situations and changeable supply chains.

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The 4 Pillars

Pillar 1

Resilience against changes in customer and societal demands and disruptions in the supply chain.

Pillar 2

Modular Technologies for flexible manufacturing operations.

Pillar 3

Simulation and interfaces to the Industrial Metaverse.

Pillar 4

Human centred technologies and upskilling.

The project proposes a holistic framework applicable to both new and existing manufacturing lines that is based on 4 pillars.

Includes design and redesign strategies for products, process chains and process planning to accommodate customer

and societal changes and optimisation of process chains across the supply chain.

Includes Industrial Strategies for distributed control and automation for modular operations, connection

with the industrial metaverse, and a Cyber-Physical service-oriented platform to support these operations.

This pillar will develop Hybrid Twins and interfaces to the Industrial Metaverse as

well as examine Virtual Commissioning for control simulations and flexible operations.

The final human centred pillar includes strategies and training to support workers achieve supply

chain optimisation and resilience against disruptions.

3 Use Case Pilot

CPPS for flexible & modular assembly of PCBs

FFT will demonstrate a flexible and modular CPPS for automatised assembly of printed circuit boards (PCBs). The hybrid assembly will be capable of automatically sensing, detecting and assembling a variety of components.

Specialized mould manufacturing for the automotive sector

EMO pilot line aims to reduce the production times, wastes, costs and energy by achieving fast response to early detection of failures at any manufacturing stage by developing a digital thread with bidirectional dataflow linking a wide range of processes.

ilots

Tools manufacturing for the aerospace

NECO's Use Case will demonstrate a flexible and modular finishing system for highly customised tabs for application in aero and windmill manufacturing sectors. This will be explored through connecting control dimensional and precision instrumentation solutions through universal and orchestrated interfaces.

Modular

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